

Photometric Study of Short Period Variable Stars

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By

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Certificate

I hereby certify that the work which is being presented in the thesis entitled "Photometric Study of Short Period Variable Stars" in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the award of the Degree of Master of Technology and submitted at Andhra University is an authentic record of my own work carried out during the period 2013-2014 under the supervision Dr. Shashikiran Ganesh and Prof. Chandana Jayaratne.

The matter presented in this thesis has not been submitted by me for the award of any other degree of this or any other Institutes/Universities.

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This is to certify that the above statement made by the candidate is correct to the best of our knowledge.

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Abstract

This thesis describes an attempt to discover short period variable stars in globular cluster M53 (NGC 5024) with the periods less than 0.2 days. To understand the nature of oscillation of short period variable stars, a detailed study was made on Delta Scuti type variable star SZ Lyn (HD 67390).

First part of the study is focused on the identification of short period variables in crowded star field of the globular cluster M53 using BVR photometry. The 1.2 m reflector telescope at Mount Abu observatory in India was used for observations during the first half of 2013. In order to identify the short period variable stars, the temporal variations of light curves were determined in deci-magnitude scale. Point Spread Function (PSF) was used for deconvolving the contaminated faint stars with the bright sources in the dense globular cluster. The light curves of over 3000 stars in the field have been tested for the variability. Light curves of 21 stars with the periods between 0.02 and 0.2 days were detected as short period variable stars.

The second part of the study is based on the observations of SZ Lyn, a large amplitude δ Scuti type binary star, using 50 cm CDK telescope at Mount Abu. The CCD detector has a sensitivity to detect deci-magnitude scale short period variables in very short exposures. To understand the periodic variations of BVR color and the behavior of the oscillations, high time resolution BVR light curves were obtained and analyzed. The study stressed on the oscillations of SZ Lyn beyond the well observed main oscillation period of 0.120 days. The well resolved light curves clearly revealed the main pulsation periods of BVR bands and the presence of their harmonics. The main pulsation periods were determined as 0.120 ± 0.003 days for B, 0.118 ± 0.010 days for V and 0.118 ± 0.002 days for R and there is no significant change of the periods with the color. Apart from the fundamental oscillation, two harmonics were also clearly detected in each band. In addition to the prominent fundamental mode of oscillation, low amplitude non-radial oscillation modes are also present in the light curves. The non-radial oscillations are characterized by oscillations in three orthogonal directions, n - radial mode, l - degree of the mode and m - azimuthal order. The degree of the mode, l for SZ Lyn was determined as $l = 1$. To the best of our knowledge this is the first time that a study on the oscillation modes of SZ Lyn is made.

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CHAPTER 1

Introduction

1.1 Variable Stars

Variable stars change their brightness and hence the apparent magnitudes fluctuate as seen from the earth. This variation of brightness may be caused by either change in emitted light by star itself or some external effects. All variable stars can be divided into two types namely intrinsic variables and extrinsic variables. The brightness of the intrinsic variables varies due to some internal cause while the brightness varies due to some external influence for extrinsic variable stars. The variable stars are further divided into seven groups: eruptive variables, pulsating variables, rotating variables, cataclysmic variables, eclipsing binary systems, optically variable X-ray sources and other miscellaneous variables. The main types of variables and their respective locations in Hertzsprung-Russell (H-R) diagram are shown in fig. 1.1.

Figure 1.1 Main types of variable stars in Hertzsprung-Russell (H-R) diagram.

This study is mainly focused on pulsating variable stars, especially very short period (<0.1 days) variables. In the first part of the study, a globular cluster M53 was investigated for detecting short period variable stars. In the second part, one of the very short period pulsating variable stars was studied in detail.

1.2 Short Period Variable Stars in Globular Cluster M53

Globular star cluster M53 (NGC 5024) RA=13h 12m 55.3s, DEC=+18° 10' 09", J2000 is one of the more outlying globulars, being about 17.5 kpc away from the Galactic center, and a distance of 18.3 kpc (Arellano et. al, 2011) from the Solar system. At this distance, its apparent angular diameter of 13' corresponds to a linear diameter of roughly 220 light years. In the latest updated version of the catalog of variables in M53 there are 62 RR Lyrae stars, 8 suspected long-period semi regular stars and 15 reported SX Phe stars (Safonova et al. 2011).

The globular cluster was subjected to detect the short period variable stars (< 0.1 days) in a very small field of view about 6×5 arc minutes. The cluster was observed in R band for a period of 3.3 hours which equals to 0.1377 days well enough to detect the desired periodicity. The short period variables are mostly pulsating type and faint stars of magnitude scale lower than $m_R=16$ magnitude. Therefore detection of variability is challenging with the low signal to noise ratio of the images. The cluster is dominated by bright sources and the faint members are convolved. Therefore the point spread function, PSF, is used to remove the bright sources and bring up the faint sources to the field. The astrometry.net is used to transform the physical coordinates to the equatorial coordinates. The detection of variability was done by VARTOOLS light curve analysis tool.

1.3 Periodic Analysis of SZ Lyncis in BVR Bands

SZ Lyncis (RA=08h 09m 35.8s, DEC=+44° 28' 17.6") is a high amplitude δ Scuti type binary star which has pulsation period of 0.1205 days and orbital period of 1173.5 days (Soliman et al., 1986). The pulsating star is the brighter component while the faint component could not be observed in spectroscopy and characterized as single line spectroscopic binary (Gazeas et al., 2004). The star has been analyzed for the periodic variations in number of times and found that the pulsation period changes

$2.25 \pm 0.42 \times 10^{-12}$ days per cycle (Paparo et al., 1988). Most of the observation considered the main pulsation period and a few attempts have been made to investigate the harmonics and secondary periods. The periodic variations in BVR color bands are not attempted. This study is focused on the periodic variations in primary, secondary and their harmonics in BVR color bands with very high time resolution light curves. In addition to that this study is attempted to find periods related to the non-radial pulsations and the degrees of the modes of pulsations.

CHAPTER 2

Stellar Pulsation

2.1 Pulsating Variables

In spite of the enormous size, the stars can oscillate. For the oscillations of the stars, there is fundamental mode of oscillation as well as the harmonics. The fundamental mode is the expansion and contraction of the star in radial direction. The figure 2.1 (a) shows the fundamental mode of oscillation analogy with the string vibration.

Figure 2.1 The modes of oscillations for a string and a star.

The figure illustrates the fundamental (a) and the first harmonic (b) modes of oscillations for string and a star. The solid and dotted lines represent the extreme positions of the string and surface of the star.

In the first harmonic one area of the star move outwards at the same time other area is moving inwards. Usually in this case the equator moves outwards and the Polar Regions move inwards. Increasing the number of loops makes the second harmonic, third harmonic and so on modes of oscillations. Increase the number of separate patches of the stellar photosphere which are simultaneously moving outwards with the adjacent patches move inwards produces very complex oscillation systems.

A star is an object where the size is set by hydrostatic equilibrium, the radiation pressure balanced by gravity. If something causes the star to expand beyond its normal size the

gravity will act to pull the star back. The moving material has a momentum, hence, it will overshoot and therefore the star will contract below its normal size. The building gas pressure will first slow down, then stop the contraction and subsequently force the star to expand. It will overshoot and cycle will repeat.

In the case of pulsating stars the enormous densities at its center make the core of the star a node. The photosphere of the star is free to oscillate so it vibrates with maximum amplitude making an antinode. The natural period of oscillation of a star is the time taken by any hypothetical vibrational disturbance created at the photosphere to the center and then reflected back to the surface. Therefore bigger stars should have longer the periods of oscillation. The fundamental period (P) of oscillation is related to the average density (ρ) of the star. The fundamental period can be estimated by the travel time of pressure wave to the center of the star of radius R and back.

$$P \sim \frac{2R}{C_s} \quad 2.1$$

where C_s is the velocity of sound.

$$C_s = \sqrt{\gamma \frac{P_g}{\rho}} \quad 2.2$$

where $\gamma = \frac{c_p}{c_v}$

At any place of the star the pressure must be balance the weight of the overlaying material. For the center of the star

$$P_g = \rho R g$$

$$P_g = \rho \frac{GM}{R} \quad 2.3$$

where G is the gravitational constant and M is the mass of the star.

$$P \sim \frac{2}{\sqrt{\gamma G}} \sqrt{\frac{R^3}{M}}$$

$$P = \text{Constant} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\rho}} \quad 2.4$$

The larger the luminosity of the pulsating star, the larger the radius and smaller the average density and the longer the period. In stars the temperature and density increases by an order of magnitude from outside towards the inside. In a star central density the amplitudes in the inner regions are extremely small and nodes for the overtone pulsations occur at different radii. More realistic cases $P_1 / P_0 = 0.687$ and $P_2 / P_1 = 0.749$ where P_0 , P_1 and P_2 are fundamental, first harmonic and second harmonic respectively.

2.2 3-D Oscillations in Stars

Stars are three dimensional and their oscillations nodes have three orthogonal directions. The three directions are r – *the radial distance*, θ - *latitude* and ϕ - *longitude*. The nodes are concentric shells at constant r , cones of constant θ and planes of constant ϕ . For 3-D stars there are three quantum numbers to specify the modes, n is related to the number of radial modes known as overtone of the mode, l is the degree of the mode and m is the azimuthal order. The displacements in r , θ and ϕ directions are given by the following equations.

$$S_r = a(r)Y_l^m(\theta, \phi) \exp(-i2\pi vt) \quad 2.5$$

$$S_\theta = b(r) \frac{\partial Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)}{\partial \theta} \exp(-i2\pi vt) \quad 2.6$$

$$S_\phi = b(r) \frac{\partial Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)}{\partial \phi} \exp(-i2\pi vt) \quad 2.7$$

where $a(r)$ and $b(r)$ are amplitudes ν is the oscillation frequency and $Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)$ are spherical harmonics given by

$$Y_l^m(\theta, \phi) = (-1)^m \sqrt{\frac{2l+1}{4\pi} \frac{(l-m)!}{(l+m)!}} P_l^m(\cos\theta) \exp(im\phi) \quad 2.8$$

where $P_l^m(\cos\theta)$ are Legendre polynomials.

The simplest mode of oscillations is radial mode with $l = 0$ and the fundamental mode is the contraction and expansion of star radially making the center of the star node and the surface anti-node (fig. 2.2a). The first overtone in radial mode is caused by concentric shell within the star. The concentric shell does not move, the motions above and the below this shell move in anti-phase (fig. 2.2b). The radial pulsation is illustrated in figure 2.2. The non-radial oscillations can be obtained by the values of $l \geq 1$ and the combinations of m .

Figure 2.2 Radial oscillations of a star. The concentric shell is shown in the dashed line.

2.3 Variable Stars in Globular Clusters

Globular cluster (GC) is a spherical shaped collection of stars mostly concentrated to the center of the cluster. Due to the higher number density of the stars, their profiles overlap each other, making it very difficult to resolve stars. The globular clusters are mainly consisting of population II stars almost formed in the time of early universe. Therefore GCs are stellar laboratories; consist of all types of stars in different phases of their lives. The globular clusters contain hundreds of thousands, and sometimes millions of stars which are strongly bound to each other gravitationally and hence the angular separation is very and the core cannot be resolved very easily even through a bigger telescope. The globular clusters are the oldest known objects in our galaxy and basically consist of population II stars which were formed in the early stage of the big bang. Since the stars in a globular cluster are presumed to have been created at about the same time by reason of their proximity, such clusters aid the study of star formation. Most globular clusters in our galaxy show a lack of O and B type stars, an

indication of their great age of 12 billion years. The globular clusters are mostly located in galactic halo.

The globular clusters have different type of stars including the main sequence, red giants, RR Lyrae, type II Cepheids, Blue Stragglers, etc. The HR diagram of globular clusters changes from the usual HR diagram in several characteristic stars and branches. The globular clusters have turnoff point which deviates from main sequence and directed to the red giant as in fig. 2.3. In addition there is a horizontal branch which contains mostly RR Lyrae stars. The Blue Stragglers are the main sequence stars which are more massive than the turning point stars. The short period variables in GCs are mostly SX Phe-type located in the blue straggler region in color-magnitude diagram (CMD) in fig. 2.3. The SX Phe-type stars are old population II stars behave like high amplitude δ Scuti stars but δ Scuti stars belong to population I stars.

Figure 2.3 Typical color – magnitude diagram of globular cluster.

CHAPTER 3

Observations

The observations were carried out at Mount Abu InfraRed observatory. The observatory is located near the town of Mount Abu in the state of Rajasthan, India. The observatory is at 24.59° N, 72.71° E and an altitude of 1680 metres with typical astronomical seeing of ~ 1.2 arc seconds and is adjacent to Guru Shikhar, the highest peak of the Aravalli Range.

3.1 The 1.2 m Telescope with Liquid Nitrogen Cooled CCD Camera

The main telescope is equatorial mounted open truss and fork type and has a 1.2 m parabolic primary ($f/3$) and 300 mm hyperbolic secondary which makes a cassegrain focus of $f/13$. The effective focal length is 15.6 m and the plate scale is $13.6''/\text{mm}$ that remains linear over the telescope field of view of 10 arc minutes diameter (Shah, 2005). The detector is Liquid Nitrogen cooled 1296×1152 CCD operating at temperature of -120 degrees C, with a field of view of 6.4×5.7 arc minutes. Liquid nitrogen cooled heads offer the ultimate performance in terms of sensitivity and dynamic range. Dark current from the chip is reduced to levels of only a few electrons per pixel per hour in some cases by cooling the CCD to approximately -120 C. The liquid nitrogen cooled heads contain a CCD mounted in a vacuum-sealed housing to minimize heat loss. The CCD is connected by a cold "finger" to a container filled with liquid nitrogen. This effectively cools the CCD to -120 °C., reducing dark current to the absolute minimum. The filter set is the UBVRI standard photometric filters.

Figure 3.1 1.2 m telescope at Mount Abu and the dome.

3.2 The 50 cm CDK Reflector and CCD Camera with Filter Wheels

The Corrected Dall-Kirkham (CDK) has a 50 cm Prolate Ellipsoid, f/3 primary mirror and 19 cm spherical secondary mirror with the effective focal ratio of f/6.8 equatorial mount telescope. The detector is 1024 x 1024 electrons multiplying (EM) CCD with the maximum cooling of -80 C and negligible read noise. The higher frame rate per second and negligible read out noise (< 1 electron with EM gain) are ideal for the observation of short period variable stars with very high time resolution. The large CCD array provides a field of view 13 X 13 arc minutes which is an advantage to observe the entire cluster in single frame. In addition to the standard UBVRI filters, a set of Polaroid sheets oriented at 0, 45 and 90 degrees are also included in the system. The telescope and the dome are fully automated through the network and can be operated remotely from PRL with all functionalities including weather monitoring.

Figure 3.2 50 cm CDK reflector telescope and the dome.

Table 3.1 Johnson and Bessell UBVRI band pass filters and their ranges.

Filter	Region in EM spectrum	Wavelength Range (nm)
U	Ultraviolet	320 – 400
B	Blue	400 – 500
V	Visible	500 – 700
R	Red	550 – 800
I	Infrared	700 – 900

3.3 Observations

The observations were mainly focused on variable stars in globular cluster, M53 (NGC 5024), RA = 13^h 12^m 55.3^s, DEC = +18° 10' 09", observed through 1.2 m telescope, 6.4 × 5.7 arc minutes field of view (FOV) in 10 consecutive nights from 5th to 14th March 2013 and 18th to 21st April 2013 in R band. Another extensive observation was done using the 0.5 m CDK telescope to investigate the star, SZ Lyn, large amplitude δ Scuti type binary, in BVR bands with a FOV 13×13 arc minutes. Since the 0.5 m CDK telescope is fully automated and can be controlled through the network, observing is relatively easy which enabled vast amount of data collection on SZ Lyn. The observations are summarized in table 3.2

Table 3.2 The observation details. The exposure time (Exp.) is in seconds and the coverage (Cov.) is in hours. The observation of SZ Lyn on 12 Dec. 2012 was done without the electron multiplying (EM) of the CCD.

Object	Globular Cluster M53		SZ Lyncis					
Instrument	1.2 m telescope		0.5 m telescope					
Band	R		B		V		R	
Date of Observation	Exp. (s)	Cov. (hr)	Exp. (s)	Cov. (hr)	Exp. (s)	Cov. (hr)	Exp. (s)	Cov. (hr)
06 Mar. 2013	40	1.19						
10 Mar. 2013	40	1.03						
12 Mar. 2013	30	3.30						
12 Dec. 2012			15	2.75	15	3.07	15	2.73
10 Dec. 2013			03	3.10	03	3.75	03	3.92
13 Dec. 2013			02	2.12	02	2.50	02	4.33
06 Jan. 2014			05	6.50	02	6.47	02	6.63
26 Jan. 2014			10	3.80	03	3.78	02	3.80
04 Feb. 2014			02	6.48	02	6.47	02	6.50

The observations of M53 globular cluster were carried out in all three bands of BVR. The long runs of R band are only mentioned in the table 3.1. B and V bands were observed, 10 frames each with the exposures of 40 seconds for the composite image of the globular cluster. The BVR composite image of globular cluster is shown in figure 3.4.

Figure 3.3 Inverted field of SZ Lyn taken by 0.5 m telescope. The field of view is 13×13 arc minutes and the exposure is 15 seconds in R band without EM gain. The comparison stars were always included for the differential photometry.

Figure 3.4 Globular star cluster M53. The image was taken with a liquid Nitrogen cooled CCD camera mounted at the Cassegrain focus of the 1.2 m telescope at Mount Abu in B, V and R filters. The field of view is 6×6 arc minutes.

CHAPTER 4

Data Analysis

4.1. Globular Cluster M53 (NGC 5024) and SZ Lyn

300 frames of R band, exposure time 30 seconds or 40 sec, covering 2.64 hours (<0.1 day) taken on 12 March 2013 were considered for the periodic analysis of M53 globular cluster. The second target was SZ Lyn, a high-amplitude δ Scuti type short period pulsating star observed in several nights covering extensive epoch for detailed investigation. Although the two targets were observed by different systems the basic data reduction steps are similar. Initially the basic corrections, bias and flat fielding were applied to all the frames. Sky flats were taken in all bands, B, V and R. The master flat was created for each band by averaging and then normalized to the mean by the **imcombine* task in IRAF. All the frames were divided by the master flat frame. The images are acquired at very low detector temperatures (-120 °C for the 1.2m telescope and -80 °C for the 50cm CDK telescope), hence the dark current is negligible and no dark corrections are made.

4.2 Centering Frames

The frames show relative movement due to the tracking and pointing errors of the telescopes during the long sequence of repeated observations. Therefore the frames should be aligned to a common center for convenience in performing photometry. For each observation set a reference frame is determined and three bright stars are selected as centering stars in the reference frame using **imexamine*. The coordinates of these centering stars were fed in to **imcentroid* algorithm to calculate the pixel shifts in x and in y directions (Δx and Δy) with respect to the three centering stars for all the frames. This x and y shift was given to the **imshift* algorithm to align all the frames. When the shift is too high relative to the given reference coordinates, coarse centering cannot be performed by increasing coarse centering radius. Therefore a new reference frame should be determined and centering is done based on the new reference frame. If the frame set is too big, as in SZ Lyn, Δx and Δy cannot be determined by **imcentroid* using the first reference frame. Therefore another reference frame should be determined to continue the centering process.

**IRAF commands*

At the end, all the centered subsets were again aligned to the foremost reference frame to make the entire frame set align to the common center, Fig 4.1. The average shift of the 238 frames of M53 globular cluster with respect to the reference frame in X pixels is 0.08 and in Y pixels is 0.34. The average shift of the centering process, for SZ Lyn data taken on 13 December 2013, for the X pixels is 0.54 and for the Y pixels is 0.17.

Figure 4.1 Flow chart of the image centering process.

Figure 4.2 Centering accuracy of 238 frames of M53 globular cluster. The shift of each frame is shown with respect to the first frame which was taken as the reference center.

Figure 4.3 Centering accuracy of 2555 frames of SZ Lyn. The shift of each frame is shown with respect to the first frame which was taken as the reference center.

4.3 Detection of Bright Stars in M53 Globular Cluster

The globular cluster M53 is densely populated cluster located in the intermediate galactic halo. The field of view of the detector is 6.4×5.7 arcmin², comparatively a small field which covers mostly the core of the cluster. Therefore the stars are more closely packed and blended which cannot be resolved easily. The detection of stars in the field was done in two phases, bright stars can be detected directly using the IRAF task *daofind*, running automatic star detection algorithm. The number of stars detected depends on the star detection threshold and minimum data value (DATA min) parameters. The expected 1σ variance in the sky is given by equation 4.1

$$1\sigma = \frac{\sqrt{s \times p + r^2}}{p} \quad (4.1)$$

s – sky value of the image in ADU

p – number of photons per ADU

r – read-noise in electron

For the 1.2m telescope imaging CCD, the number of photons per ADU is 1 and the read-noise in electron is 7. The star detection threshold is usually taken as $3.5 \times 1\sigma$ and the DATA min is $s - 3\sigma$. The equation is a good approximation to initiate the threshold value and then change it appropriately to select the desired number of stars in the field. The value of detection threshold 20 and minimum data value of -10 were fed in to *daofind* task and selected 1259 bright stars in the field with a magnitude smaller than 16 in the first phase of detection of stars.

4.4 Detection of Faint Stars in M53 Globular Cluster - Point Spread Function (PSF)

The globular cluster is more crowded with the faint stars in the background and most of these faint stars are merged with the bright stars. In this regard the contribution of atmospheric seeing is more and hence the star's image is spread out in number of pixels and also causes the shape of the image vary with time (from image to another). Hence aperture selection contains the counts from the star as well as light from the sky background. The sky signal must be accurately measured and subtracted from the pixels containing the star and sky signal. Stars in rich clusters are usually overlapped and somehow must be found to separate the light from neighboring stars. This effect is called the contamination.

The Point Spread Function (PSF) is the shape of point source of light. In practice the poor telescope focus and tracking errors and atmospheric seeing can contribute to degradation of the PSF.

In order to build the PSF the best frame out of 238 frames was selected by examining the star marked in fig. 4.4 for each frame. The FWHM, eccentricity and flux of the star in each frame were measured by fitting radial profile in IRAF *imexamine* task. The eccentricity is a vital parameter to decide the best frame since it reflects the degradation effects of PSF such as atmospheric seeing and telescope tracking errors. Therefore the optimum frame was selected for modeling the PSF by examining the parameters of FWHM, eccentricity and flux.

Figure 4.4 Inverted image of M53.

The marked star is taken for analysis of parameters FWHM, eccentricity and the flux. In this frame, the FWHM and eccentricity for the marked star were 2.98 and 0.05 respectively

The access of the faint stars can be done only after eliminating the bright stars from the field. One common way of doing this is to build a PSF function for the IRAF image using stars selected, from the input photometry file. A set of PSF stars should be selected from the list.

The PSF star should have the following characteristics.

- No other star contributes any light within one fitting radius of the selected star.
- Stars lie near the selected star should be very faint.
- There are no bad columns, rows and bad pixels near the selected star.

Suitable PSF stars are normally selected interactively using the image display and image cursor and matched with the stars in *photfile* using the cursor position and a tolerance specified by the *matchrad* parameter in the *daopars* task. A star must be in the photometry file before it can be used as a PSF star. If a match is found, PSF checks that the candidate star is not too close to the edge of the image and that it contains no bad pixels as defined by *datamin* and *datamax* in the *datapars* task. After selection a mesh, contour, or profile plot of the data subraster around the candidate star is displayed in the graphics window, PSF enters graphics cursor command mode and given the option to accept or reject the star. If accepts the star it is added to the PSF star list.

Figure 4.5 Mesh plot of point spread function of the star marked in fig 4.4

19 bright well resolved stars were selected from the frame M53R0158 to construct the PSF model. The PSF radius (*psfrad*) and the fitting radius (*fitrad*) were set to 11 and 3 pixels respectively. The PSF function was first applied to selected stars and subsequently applied to all stars in the photometry file. The results are in fig. 4.7.

The neighbor star can be defined in equation 4.2. For this study, the PSF model was applied by defining the neighboring stars within 23.5 pixels. The PSF model is shown in fig. 4.6 with the pixel scale.

$$\frac{1.5 \text{ psfrad}}{\text{scale}} + \frac{2.0 \times \text{fitrad}}{\text{scale}} + 1 \text{ pixel} \quad (4.2)$$

Figure 4.6 The inverted image of the PSF Model.

The scale is in pixels and total width and height is 47×47 pixels determined by the equation 4.2. The dark black area is the star enclosing 11 pixels and surrounding to that some contribution of faint stars are also presented.

4.5 Extraction of Instrumental Magnitudes

Measuring the instrumental magnitudes for a crowded field is very difficult due to the contamination and difficulty of measuring the true sky level. A circular aperture should be defined to extract the flux from the stars considering several aspects such as the brightness of the star, the circular symmetry, the sky background and the convolution of fluxes from the objects in the vicinity. In IRAF the algorithm *phot* is used to measure the instrumental magnitudes with some parameter editing to define the appropriate aperture. Several parameters are crucial in the aperture selection.

Figure 4.8 The arrangement of aperture parameters

Figure 4.9 The radial profile of the star marked in fig.4.4

This was obtained by the interactive task in IRAF called ‘imexamine’. The very important outputs of this task are FWHM of the Gaussian profile, ellipticity, peak value and the position angel of the two dimensional Gaussian profile.

The appropriate measurement aperture was selected by examining the radial profiles of few bright stars in the field. The radial profile gives the FWHM of the Gaussian profile of the selected stars. A typical radial profile is shown in the fig. 4.9.

It was a challenging task to define a common aperture for a set of stars in the field. The aperture is usually set to 3 or 4 times the FWHM to include all the lights from the star within the aperture and at the same time make sure not to include too much of background to the aperture. The radial profiles of several bright stars were taken and then average FWHM is estimated that define aperture radius for *phot*. In addition to the aperture radius several

parameters in fig. 4.8 have to be defined. To model the value of the sky, the size and the location of the annulus have to be defined. In that case the sky was defined 5 pixels from the aperture and the width of the sky annulus was set to 5 pixels in the case of bright stars in the field. But when goes to faint stars where the stars are more closer to each other and the signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) is very low after applying PSF, the sky annulus should be chosen close to the star and the width was set to less than 5 pixels. The selected parameters values for *phot* are in table 1.

Table 4.1 Important parameters for extraction of instrumental magnitudes

Parameter	Bright Stars	Faint Stars (After PSF model applied)
FWHM	3	6
Aperture	9	9
Annulus	11	12
DAnnulus	3	5
Sigma	2	2.8

Using the above parameters there were 1259 instrumental magnitudes extracted for the set of bright stars and another 1900 instrumental magnitudes were extracted for the set of faint stars for the interval of 0.1377 days. The typical magnitude range for the bright stars is $12 < m_R < 16$ and that for the faint stars is $16 < m_R < 20$.

4.6 Astrometry

The astrometric transformation between the pixels and celestial coordinates for the reference was done by astrometry.net code. Astrometry.net is developed by Lang and Hogg (2010) and works under UNIX environment. In this code the image is solved by mapping the sky images with the given image, using pattern recognition technique of the selected stars in the field. In order to reduce the time for solution, the right ascension (RA) and declination (DEC) and the field of view (FOV) of the reference image can be specified. The reference image was fed in to the stand alone astrometry.net system in local machine and the image was produced with the world coordinate system (WCS) which is right ascension (RA) and declination (DEC) coordinates. The solve field script was used in astrometry.net to solve the field of the reference image. The pixel coordinates were transformed to equatorial coordinates updating the header file with the parameters listed in table 4.2. For the reference image the field size is 6.38×5.68 arc minutes and the pixel dimension is 648×576 . The pixel scale in X and in Y direction is 0.591 arc seconds per pixel. According to the fig. 4.2 the average frame shift of

238 frames of globular cluster in X direction is 0.08 pixels and in Y direction 0.34 pixels. This results the average centering error in RA is 0.047 arc seconds and in DEC it is 0.2 arc seconds.

The image format given in astrometry.net after the coordinate transformation is different with the image format use in IRAF. The pixel coordinates will be changed by the process. Therefore the image header keywords updated by the astrometry.net were taken and updated the IRAF image. The following keywords were updated in the IRAF image and the IRAF task, *wcsctran* was used for the coordinate transformation.

Table 4.2 The header parameters generated by astrometry.net for the reference image to calculate the world coordinates using the *wcsctran* algorithm.

Keyword	Value	Remarks
WCSAXES	2	Number of axes
CTYPE1	RA-TAN-SIP	RA in tangent plane projection
CTYPE2	DEC-TAN-SIP	DEC in tangent plane projection
CRVAL1	198.2402	RA at the reference pixel in degrees
CRVAL2	18.16970	DEC at the reference pixel in degrees
CRPIX1	378.8833	reference pixel on first axis
CRPIX2	287.2014	reference pixel on second axis
CUNIT1	Deg.	
CUNIT2	Deg.	
CD1_1	1.640266×10^{-4}	change in RA per pixel along first axis evaluated at reference pixel
CD1_2	7.091997×10^{-6}	change in RA per pixel along second axis evaluated at reference pixel
CD2_1	-7.161442×10^{-6}	change in DEC per pixel along first axis evaluated at reference pixel
CD2_2	1.640582×10^{-4}	change in DEC per pixel along second axis evaluated at reference pixel

The pixel coordinates of the reference image taken from the photometry file were transformed to world coordinates. Since all 238 frames of globular cluster were aligned with in a pixel (see fig. 4.2 and fig. 4.3) the WCS solutions for all the frames can be taken as the WCS of the reference frame. The following table shows the difference of the WCS with standard WCS of the M53.

Table 4.3 The difference of the RA and DEC of 8 bright stars chosen in the field of the reference image of M53 globular cluster. The stars were selected covering the entire field and the offset were calculated with respect to the standard coordinate taken from the sky atlas.

ID	Sky Atlas		Observation		Offset	
	RA- α (h:m:s)	DEC - δ ($^{\circ}$: $'$: $''$)	RA - α (h:m:s)	DEC - δ ($^{\circ}$: $'$: $''$)	α ($''$)	δ ($''$)
134	13:12:56.95	18:08:41.90	13:12:56.95	18:08:41.96	0.00	0.06
153	13:12:50.43	18:08:53.70	13:12:50.42	18:08:53.74	0.01	0.04
470	13:13:03.67	18:08:38.80	13:13:03.67	18:09:38.88	0.00	0.08
1019	13:13:04.67	18:10:59.50	13:13:04.68	18:10:59.45	0.01	0.05
1106	13:12:45.49	18:11:29.30	13:12:45.53	18:11:29.00	0.04	0.30
1163	13:12:49.87	18:11:49.50	13:12:48.97	18:11:48.80	0.90	0.70
1173	13:13:03.32	18:11:44.00	13:13:03.34	18:11:43.51	0.02	0.49
1181	13:12:49.03	18:11:57.90	13:12:49.27	18:11:56.83	0.24	1.07

4.7 Lomb-Scargle Periodogram

The determination of instrumental magnitudes of 3159 stars of globular cluster was directed to check for variability. Due to the large numbers of stars, it is necessary to automate the detection of variable sources. To solve the large array 238 \times 3159 magnitudes, VARTOOLS software package (Hartman et al., 2008) is used. The VARTOOLS program is a command line utility that provides tools for processing and analyzing astronomical time series data. It includes methods for calculating variability and periodicity statistics of light curves. The Lomb – Scargle (LS) periodogram (Lomb, 1976) is used for variability testing as the algorithm is designed to pick out periodic variation in unevenly sampled data. The Lomb-Scargle period-finding algorithm applied on the light curves search for periods between 0.1 and 0.2 days at a frequency resolution of 0.1/T where T is the time-span of the light curve which is 0.13774 days. The output was set to report the highest peak, and output the periodogram. Each light curve was pre-whitened and re-applies L-S before finding the next peak, and uses a 5 sigma iterative clipping in determining the spectroscopic signal-to-noise. For each peak it will output the period found, the logarithm of the formal false alarm probability (LS Probability), and the spectroscopic signal to noise ratio (SNR) for the peaks ($SNR = (LS - \langle LS \rangle) / RMS(LS)$; where LS is the normalized L-S statistic). LS probability is the log value of false alarm probability that the probability of detecting a signal from noise. An unlike good fit which has very small LS probability interpreted of detection of corresponding period.

Therefore the criteria to select the variability is

$$\text{LS Probability (False Alarm Probability)} < 10^{-4}$$

The table 5.1 and 5.2 shows the variable stars which have false probability less than 10^{-4} . The smaller the false alarm probability, finer the detection of periodicity determined by the LS periodogram (Scargle, 1982).

In order to process for the LS periodogram, the input text files should contained three columns namely Julian date, magnitude and the error of the magnitude. For the total 3159 stars, text files were created by running a macro in EXCEL.

4.8 Reduction of BVR bands of SZ Lyn

The high time resolution data in color bands, B, V and R, of SZ Lyn were subjected to different analysis in order to interpret the wavelength dependence of the variability. The basic variability test, the differential magnitude was done using a bright star in vicinity of SZ Lyn called comparison 1 in fig 3.3. The differential magnitudes were plotted in all three color bands in fig. 5.5. In photometry it is very useful to observe the difference of the colors, B – V and V – R against time. In this regard, the B, V and R values have to be simultaneous to calculate the difference. Since the observations were time series, it is impossible to have simultaneous values in B, V and R. In order to get the simultaneous values the spline interpolation was performed for the light curves. B band light curve was subjected to the cubic spline interpolation and calculated the coefficients of spline curve. Then B magnitudes were determined for the time stamps of V band to get the common magnitudes for B and V. The script is written in Python language. Figure 4.10 shows the approximation of the interpolated values and the true values of the B band magnitudes. The interpolation highly depends on the smoothing parameter, S. There is a critical smoothing parameter (S) to make the interpolated values very much close to the observed values. If S is less than or greater than the ideal value the interpolated values will be deviated from actual values.

Figure 4.10 Cubic spline interpolation of B band light curve of SZ Lyn for 4 February 2014 observation. The red line shows the cubic spline function fitted to the observed values with the smoothing parameter, $S = 0.15$. The blue dots are the interpolated values for Julian days taken from V band observation for same day. The rectangular box area in panel (a) is magnified in panel (b) to show approximation of the interpolation.

4.9 Detection of Pulsation Periods in BVR bands of SZ Lyn

The extensive observation of SZ Lyn in BVR bands have been subjected for a pulsation investigation. Apart from the main pulsation the data were investigated for secondary frequencies using VARTOOLS. The LS algorithm was run for searching the periods between 0.01 and 0.2 with the frequency resolution of $0.01/T$ where T is the span of light curves. The process searched for three peaks with pre-whitened data and used a 5 sigma iterative clipping in determining the spectroscopic signal-to-noise. The power spectrum of each light curve for BVR bands were produced in the output.

CHAPTER 5

Results

5.1 Light Curves and Periods of New Short Period Variables in M53

After extraction of instrumental magnitudes in R band the individual magnitudes were examined for variability. In this process individual magnitude files were created with three columns namely the Julian day of the particular observation time and the corresponding instrumental magnitude and error. This file format is necessary to feed the data in to VARTOOLS, software designed for light curve analysis. The variability is tested for the period between 0.01 and 0.2 days with the frequency resolution of $0.01/T$, where T is the time span of light curve. The suspected candidates found by this process are presented as variables in table 5.1 and their light curves are also shown in figure 5.1

Table 5.1 The short period variable stars detected in the globular cluster M53. This set of stars is higher magnitude stars picked up before PSF is applied. The Lomb-Scargle probability (LS_Pro) is also included to show strength of determination of the periodicity. LS_Pro is the powers of ten.

ID	RA	DEC	LS_Pro	Period (days)
V16-1	13:12:57.12	18:07:40.58	-13.798	0.14654
V95-3	13:12:57.00	18:08:24.00	-13.280	0.12873
V108-4	13:12:47.74	18:08:35.92	-26.860	0.16596
V121-5	13:12:51.43	18:08:38.54	-09.265	0.02937
V155-6	13:12:44.38	18:08:57.66	-11.349	0.13373
V162-8	13:12:45.38	18:08:59.53	-13.689	0.15653
V172-9	13:12:45.38	18:09:02.05	-17.250	0.15833
V570-11	13:12:52.13	18:10:00.23	-13.250	0.15477
V857-12	13:12:50.69	18:10:39.68	-09.615	0.08773
V920-13	13:12:58.27	18:10:43.21	-11.133	0.12995
V1190-14	13:12:48.17	18:12:02.38	-11.039	0.12637

Figure 5.1 Light curves of the detected variable stars in globular cluster M53. 238 magnitudes of 30 seconds exposure in R band were included in each light curve.

Figure 5.1 Continued

Table 5.2 The short period variable stars detected in the globular cluster M53. This set of stars is lower magnitude stars picked up after PSF is applied. The LS probability is also included to show strength of determination the periodicity. The stars are very faint and the signal to noise ratio is also very low causing the low LS probability and reduce the strength of the periodicity determination.

ID	RA	DEC	LS_Pro	Period(days)
V264-1	13:12:51.62	18:08:41.17	-11.448	0.02744
V353-2	13:12:49.97	18:08:56.80	-06.219	0.08200
V542-3	13:12:59.20	18:09:18.25	-05.325	0.03241
V729-4	13:12:53.83	18:09:44.93	-12.547	0.07738
V1165-5	13:12:52.27	18:10:35.83	-18.343	0.12522
V1178-6	13:12:52.90	18:10:36.16	-05.590	0.03418
V1388-7	13:12:52.27	18:11:05.06	-12.570	0.07366
V1628-8	13:12:59.81	18:11:39.59	-10.168	0.02420
V1681-9	13:12:57.17	18:11:50.75	-09.434	0.08450
V1853-10	13:12:49.70	18:12:47.16	-10.450	0.07148

Figure 5.2 Light curves of the detected variable stars in globular cluster M53. 238 magnitudes of 30 seconds exposure in R band were included in each light curve. This set of stars was selected from 1900 stars after applying PSF function.

Figure 5.2 Continued.

5.2 Light Curves and Oscillation Periods of SZ Lyn

The star SZ Lyncis is a large-amplitude delta Scuti-type binary variable star which has a pulsation period of 0.12052115 days (Moffett et al., 1987). The pulsating star is the brighter component of the binary and it has a spectral range from A7-F2 (Kholopov et al., 1985). The pulsating star is observed in three bands, B, V and R, with a very high time resolution for detecting pulsations in addition to the main pulsation period of 0.1205 days. In this observation the pulsation variations in B, V and R bands were examined separately and pulsation periods determined using VARTOOLS. The light curves and the L-S power spectra shown in figure 5.3 for the observations of 6 days in different epoch in year 2012, 2013 and 2014.

Figure 5.3 The light curves of SZ Lyn in B,V and R bands (left plates) and the corresponding L-S power spectra in B, V and R bands (right plates). The three colors blue, green and red represent the three wavelength band of B, V and R respectively. The date of observation is mentioned in each plate.

Figure 5.3 Continued.

5.3 Light Curves of B - V and V - R of SZ Lyn

Figure 5.4 The variation of B, V and R magnitudes of SZ Lyn and B – V and V - R for the data taken on 6 January 2014. B-V and V-R were shifted by 11.8 and 12 magnitudes respectively in order to bring to the vicinity of B, V and R. V and R magnitudes were interpolated values referred to the Julian days of B band. V- R magnitudes have been removed after 0.363298 JD since the R data is fluctuated as shown in red curve.

Figure 5.5 The variation of B, V and R magnitudes of SZ Lyn and B – V and V-R for the data taken on 4 February 2014. The B magnitude was shifted by 0.8 and B-V and V-R were shifted by 11.5 and 12.7 magnitudes respectively in order to bring to the vicinity of V and R. B and R magnitudes were interpolated values referred to the Julian days of V band.

SZ lyn was subjected to differential photometry with the comparison stars in the field (Figure 3.3). The differential photometry was performed with the same aperture size since the size, i.e. FWHM of the Gaussian profile, of the SZ lyn and the two comparison stars are almost same. The comparison was done for the data taken on 4th February 2014.

Figure 5.6 The comparison of the magnitude variation of SZ Lyn with the comparison star 1 for the observation on 4th February 2014. Left plates: Blue, Green and Red represent the BVR bands respectively and black shows the comparison star. Right plates: The differential magnitudes in BVR bands with respect to the comparison star.

Table 5.3 The pulsation periods of SZ Lyn. Three pulsation periods (labeled as P_1 , P_2 and P_3) for each of the BVR bands were clearly identified and listed in the table below. The error is the standard deviation of the mean and the average is rounded off to the error.

Date	Period (days)								
	B			V			R		
	P_1	P_2	P_3	P_1	P_2	P_3	P_1	P_2	P_3
24 Dec 2012	0.12441	0.05723	0.02680	0.13470	0.06529	0.01996	0.11978	0.05445	0.01064
10 Dec 2013	0.11841	0.05788	0.03796	0.12929	0.05568	0.01032	0.15266	0.04995	0.01942
13 Dec 2013	0.09591	0.04412	0.02436	0.09821	0.03928	0.02302	0.12437	0.06176	0.04304
06 Jan 2014	0.11770	0.07050	0.01340	0.12027	0.06053	0.04247	0.11604	0.06017	0.03857
26 Jan 2014	0.11921	0.05233	0.03934	0.11760	0.06038	0.03517	0.11645	0.05954	0.03744
04 Feb 2014	0.11886	0.01354	0.01289	0.11004	0.06004	0.03533	0.11626	0.05927	0.01223
Average	0.116±0.010	0.049±0.020	0.023±0.009	0.118±0.013	0.057±0.009	0.028±0.012	0.124±0.014	0.058±0.017	0.027±0.012

CHAPTER 6

Discussion

21 stars have been identified as variables in globular cluster M53 (NGC 5024). The light curves of 3159 stars in R band covering 0.1377 days were subjected to the analysis to find out the variables of less than 0.1 day variability. Variability of less than 0.1 days is usually categorized as very short period variables and faint stars with the amplitude change less than 1 magnitude. Therefore detection of variables, with small periods and small change in magnitudes, is very complicated in very dense globular clusters. Variable stars with light curves above the threshold of detection are shown in fig. 6.1.

Figure 6.1 The variable stars identified in M53 globular cluster.

Plate **a** shows the variable stars identified in higher magnitude scale. 14 stars were detected as variables in the field. Plate **b** shows the variable stars identified after the PSF fitting. Refer to the ID numbers in table 5.1 and table 5.2

The stars V121-5 and V857-12 in figure 6.1(a) detected as the periodicity less than 0.1 days by the Lomb-Scargle Periodogram algorithm. The light curves of V121 and V857 are expected to have just more than one cycle but the light curves in fig. 5.1 do not clearly show the periodicity. Therefore differential magnitudes of the two stars were determined with respect to the non-variable, similar magnitude star in the field. The resultant light curves are shown in fig. 6.2. The short-period characteristic shapes in globular clusters are classified as SX Phe stars which have the periods between 0.03 and 0.14 days (Safonova, 2011). In addition to that SX Phe stars show multiple frequencies of light variations which is revealed in the differential light curve of star V121. The main periodicity of V121 was determined as

0.02937 days which is shown in fig. 6.2 and in addition to the main pulsation there is a secondary frequency or a harmonic of the main pulsation given by a Fourier fitting. There is a lack of data points around the Julian day 2456364.62 because some of the data points were removed due to a systematic deviation. The amplitude of the variability of V121 is around 0.3 magnitudes for the main period and 0.1 magnitudes for the secondary pulsation. The amplitude of V857 is even small which is around 0.02 magnitudes. Based on all these characteristics of the light curves, the stars V121 and V857 can be classified as delta-scuti type variables. These two stars were not discovered in the previous extensive studies of globular cluster M53.

Figure 6.2 Differential magnitude of stars V121 and V857. The trend lines are Fourier fittings with root mean square error (RMSE) of 0.11 for V121 and 0.01 for V857.

Figure 6.3 Instrumental magnitudes of a comparison star.

For comparison of magnitude variations in the variable stars found in globular cluster, the temporal distribution of magnitudes of a stable star can be used. The average magnitude

variation due to the atmospheric seeing and other effect can be seen in fig. 6.3. The variation is clearly in the order of centi-magnitude scale. The magnitude variations in the variable stars found in this study were deci-magnitude scale conformed that the variations are due to the intrinsic brightness changes.

In this analysis the detection threshold of variability is taken as the false alarm probability which is given as the logarithm of L-S probability in L-S periodogram. This is a measure of how good is the detected periodicity in the light curve. The table 5.1 and 5.2 show the list of variables stars detected and also mentioned the L-S probability of the detected periods. However the L-S probabilities for the bright stars were quite higher than those for faint stars. This is because the faint stars were taken after the PSF fitting and the PSF fitting itself added noise resulting in low signal-to-noise ratio. Hence the light curves were much scattered and the periodicity detection is also very poor. The two faint stars V353 and V542 detected in this study, earlier detected by Safonova (2011), named as SX6 and SX20 respectively, have different periods compared to the previous observations. Although the observation conformed that there is variability in these stars the determination of periods has large uncertainties.

The second part of the analysis is focused on the short period variable star, SZ Lyn. The main periodicity was well determined in several observations and the recent estimation is 0.1205 days (Gazeas et al., 2004). The investigations of the periodicity in BVR color bands are rare for delta-scuti type short period variables and this study addressed the above area extensively. One of the objectives of the investigation is to study

Figure 6.4 Typical variations of four properties with time for δ Cephei. The radius in units of minimum radius, temperature in K and velocity in ms^{-1} . Image credited to Gerald North.

the potential periodic variations in BVR bands. The averaged periods of the fundamental mode for BVR bands are almost same within the errors (Table 5.3) and there is no significant change with the color.

Both radial and non-radial oscillations occur in Delta Scuti stars. Although SZ lyn shows very prominent fundamental mode of oscillation, there are low amplitude non-radial modes clearly visible in the light curves. The light curves obtained on 6 January 2014 and 4 February 2014 has slight deviations from symmetry (fig. 5.3) in two complete cycles revealing the presence of non-radial pulsations. In addition the figure 5.4 shows there is a fluctuation in magnitudes in the lowering phase while the rising phase of the magnitude is very smooth. The variation of magnitude, temperature and radius of typical δ -Cephei is given in the fig. 6.4. According to the explanation the magnitude maxima and minima both occur in equilibrium radius. The observation shows there is some fluctuations in the light curves in the magnitude lowering phase which corresponding to decrease in radius. The star compresses in this phase generating restoring force and produce non-radial pulsations in higher orders of l and m . These non-radial pulsations occur at less than the equilibrium radius and therefore star is relatively smaller making the amplitude of oscillations very small. With a limited signal-to-noise ratio the lowering phase is then appeared as a fluctuation of magnitudes.

The periods obtained in this study, P_1 , P_2 and P_3 are interrelated as $P_1 \sim 2P_2$ and $P_1 \sim 3P_3$ for all bands and can be determined as fundamental, first overtone and the second overtone respectively. Similar results were obtained by Gazeas in 2004. The ratio of the fundamental period and the harmonics provides information of the temperature and the pressure gradients and as well as density stratification in the variable stars. The following table shows the periodic ratios calculated for SZ Lyn from the data obtained in table 5.3.

B		V		R	
P_2/P_1	P_3/P_2	P_2/P_1	P_3/P_2	P_2/P_1	P_3/P_2
0.422	0.469	0.483	0.491	0.468	0.466

For Delta Scuti type stars the ratio of first overtone to fundamental would be 0.77 (Kurtz, 2010) and according to more realistic polytrope this ratio would become 0.687 (Erika, 1993). In this model a central density is larger and the amplitudes in the inner regions are extremely

small since quite large mass has to be moved. The calculated average value of $P_2/P_1 = 0.458$ is less than the model value of either 0.770 or 0.687, conforming the low central density concentration of SZ Lyn.

Delta Scuti stars fall in an extension of the Cepheid instability strip, close to the main sequence. They typically have masses around 2 – 2.5 solar mass and are either near or just after the end of core hydrogen burning. In the Cepheids and RR Lyrae stars typically only a single period is observed, in most cases the fundamental radial mode only. The stars near the main sequence, like SZ Lyn, generally show several periods making them potentially more interesting for investigation of stellar interiors. It can be clearly seen from fig. 5.4 that the amplitude of pulsation decreases as the wavelength increases. In the rising phase the B - V and the V - R both increase as shown in the fig. 5.4. This means the SZ Lyn moves in the spectral range from type F to type A with the pulsation.

It is possible to identify the oscillation modes from multicolor photometry. The intensity change is much greater in blue than in red due to the blackbody nature. Most pulsating stars will have larger photometric variations in blue than in red. This fact is observed in the results showing the magnitude variations of SZ Lyn in BVR where $\Delta B \sim 0.7$, $\Delta V \sim 0.5$ and $\Delta R \sim 0.4$ in fig. 5.4. In addition to this basic effect, the light variations in different wavelengths depend on the temperature variations and change in geometrical cross-section. It is possible to determine the spherical degree, l from the amplitude difference in different wavelength bands. Therefore observation of light in BVR can be used to find the degree l of the mode (Kurtz, 2010). The theoretical predictions of amplitude ratios for various degrees l is shown in the fig. 6.5 for a typical B2 star and for typical F2 star.

The observations were carried out only for BVR system. From the available data the degree l of the mode was estimated using the amplitude ratios of BVR with respect to the B band amplitude. The data taken on 6 January 2014 and 4 February 2014 were taken for analysis and the result is presented in fig. 6.6. SZ Lyn is F2 type star. The theoretical model of F2 type star shown in fig. 6.5 can be used to approximate the observations shown in fig. 6.5. According to the theoretical model of F2 type star and degree $l = 1$ oscillation mode, the distribution of B, V and R ratios is linear with the wavelength. This was matched with the observation results. Therefore $l = 1$ mode of theoretical model is highly in line with the

observations. Thus it can be determined SZ Lyn is also oscillating non-radially in degree $l = 1$ mode.

Figure 6.5 Theoretical predicted amplitude ratios for various degrees of l of a typical B2 star (left) and of a typical F2 star (right). The line styles, continuous for $l = 0$, dashed for $l = 1$, dashed-dot for $l = 2$, dotted for $l = 3$ and dashed-dot-dot-dotted for $l = 4$. A_x is the filters represent U, B₁, B, B₂, V₁, V, G. Image source: Astroseismology, D.W. Kurtz.

Figure 6.6 The variation of amplitude ratios of SZ Lyn for two observations days, full for 6 January 2014 and dashed for 4 February 2014. Note that the B band amplitude ratios overlapped. The A_x represents the B, V and R band amplitudes and A_B represents the amplitude of B band.

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Appendix

Script files written in IRAF

```
/// This script is written to filter the images to B, V and R
band separately and make lists ///
```

```
while(fscan(list,s1) != EOF) {
  imgets((s1), "FILTA")
  s2 = (imgets.value)
  print((s1), >>(s2) // ".list")
  print(s2)
}
```

```
-----
-
```

```
/// This script is written to extract the Julian Days of the
image file list ///
```

```
list = "B.list"
while(fscan(list,s1) != EOF) {
  imgets((s1), "JD")
  s2 = (imgets.value)
  print((s2), >> "Bdjlist")
}
```

```
-----
-
```

```
/// This script is used to write the output of imexamine task
in a text file ///
```

```
list="B.list"
imexamine.keeplog=yes
imexamine.logfile="center.log"
while(fscan(list,s1)!=EOF){
  display((s1), zscale-, zrange-, z1=0, z2=1000)
  imexam((s1))
}
```

```
/// This script is written to rename the images ///
```

```
for (i=1; i<=552; i+=1)
list="V.list"
while(fscan(list,s1)!= EOF){
if (i < 10)
rename(s1, "sz00"//i)
s2="sz00"//i
  else if (i < 100)
    rename(s1, "sz0"//i)
    s2="sz0"//i
      else (i < 553)
        rename(s1, "sz"//i)
        s2="sz"//i
print(s2)
}
```

```
-----
--
```

```
/// Macro script is written to extract the magnitudes for each
star individually from the output magnitude file of 'phot'
task in IRAF. The magnitude file is a one whole file with more
than 1000 stars and the magnitudes written. The program is
separated each star and written to separate file to input for
the VARTOOL periodic analysis software ///
```

```
/// This Macro file is written by Mr. Saraj Gunasekera, Space
Applications Division, and ACCIMT///
```

```
Sub Janaka2()
```

```
For i = 1 To 1900
```

```
    Worksheets("Sheet2").Activate
    Selection.Range("$A$1:$A$299642").AutoFilter Field:=1,
Criteria:=i
    Range("B:C").Select
    Selection.Copy
    Sheets("Sheet1").Select
    Range("B1").Select
    ActiveSheet.Paste
```

```
Open "D:\list\M53\M53Star" & i For Output As #1
```

```
    For j = 1 To 238
        If i = 1 Then
            Print #1, Cells(j + 1, 1); Spc(5); Cells(j, 2);
Spc(5); Cells(j, 3)
        Else
            Print #1, Cells(j + 1, 1); Spc(5); Cells(j + 1, 2);
Spc(5); Cells(j + 1, 3)
        End If
    Next j
```

```
Close #1
```

```
Next i
```

```
End Sub
```

```
/// Script is written in Python to interpolate the light curves. For
B - V magnitudes, B and V have to be determined in the same time.
The observations were carried out continuously and no common
observation in B, V and R magnitudes. The light curve of B was
interpolated for the time prints of V to get the common timings. ///
```

```
>>> import numpy as np
>>> import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
>>> from scipy import interpolate
>>> jd = 'jd.txt'
>>> x = np.loadtxt(jd, dtype='f4')
>>> x
array([ 0.19261573,  0.19265047,  0.1927662 , ...,  0.46233797,
        0.46238425,  0.46241897], dtype=float32)
>>> b = 'b.txt'
>>> y = np.loadtxt(b, dtype='f4')
>>> y
array([ 12.39799976,  12.42000008,  12.40999985, ...,  13.15400028,
        13.14099979,  13.18900013], dtype=float32)
>>> plt.figure()
<matplotlib.figure.Figure object at 0xacf2fcc>
>>> plt.plot(x,y,'xr')
[<matplotlib.lines.Line2D object at 0xadc7fcc>]
>>> plt.show()
>>> tck = interpolate.splrep(x,y, s=0)
>>> jdvdv = 'jdvdv.txt'
>>> xnew = np.loadtxt(jdvdv, dtype='f4')
>>> ynew = interpolate.splev(xnew, tck, der=0)
>>> plt.figure()
<matplotlib.figure.Figure object at 0xadc26ec>
>>> plt.plot(x,y,'-r',xnew,ynew,'xb')
[<matplotlib.lines.Line2D object at 0xaedae0c>,
 <matplotlib.lines.Line2D object at 0xaedaf0c>]
>>> plt.show()
```